

Task 1.2 – Pilot region report: Osrednjeslovenska regija

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INDEX

1. The Pilot Region	3
2. The emerging functions of the Pilot Region	15
3. Main differences between rural areas within the Pilot Region	19
4. The main transition challenges	21
5. The state of knowledge and information needs.....	22
6. Conclusions.....	22
7. References.....	24

1. The Pilot Region

1.1 The concerned territory.

The central Slovenian statistical (NUTS3) region (Osrednjeslovenska regija) is the most densely populated and urbanized Slovenian region, especially in the central part (Ljubljana and the areas of the Ljubljana Plain and the Kamniškobistriška Plain). There are also some other heavily urbanized and densely populated areas along the edge of the Ljubljana Marshes (Brezovica – Vrhnika) and the south-eastern edge of the region (Lavrica – Škofljica), as well as the area around Grosuplje (Šmarje Sap – Grosuplje) (MOP, 2019).

[Table 1: Urban settlements in the Osrednjeslovenska region \(MOP, 2019\)](#)

Name of settlement	Status of city
Ljubljana	Yes
Domžale	Yes
Kamnik	Yes
Grosuplje	Yes
Logatec	Yes
Vrhnika	Yes
Borovnica	No
Brezovica pri Ljubljani	No
Ig	No
Lavrica	No
Medvode	Yes
Mengeš	Yes
Škofljica	No
Trzin	No
Vir	No
Višnja Gora	Yes
Vnanje Gorice	No

Ljubljana is the capital of the country, where the seat of the Government of the Republic of Slovenia is located. It has a branched system of social infrastructure at the state and local level, as it provides social infrastructure for all central national institutions.

In addition to Ljubljana, social infrastructure for the performance of higher-level functions is also being strengthened in settlements that perform the role 3rd level centres (Domžale, Kamnik), that is for tertiary and secondary level of health care, higher education, judicial and administrative institutions, specialized social care and public research institutions. In 4th level centres, (Vrhnika, Logatec, Grosuplje) at least a health centre is provided, as well as local offices of (decentralized) state administration. (MOP, 2019)

Table 2: Population and area in the Osrednjeslovenska region. Source: Rural observatory.

	POPULATION	TOTAL AREA (ha)	% of total NUTS3 area	% of total NUTS3 population	% of total NUTS2 area	% of total NUTS2 population
Cities	293.218	27.503	11,8%	52,8%	3,5%	29,2%
Town and suburban areas	172.579	99.542	42,6%	31,1%	31,1%	45,0%
Rural areas	89.416	106.367	45,6%	16,1%	65,4%	25,8%
TOTAL (NUTS3)	555.213	233.412				
TOTAL (NUTS3)	1.003.393	783.970				

This region is an above-average developed area; it is characterized by demographic development, population growth (i.e. a positive natural growth and migration balance). The concentration of population is related to growing urbanization and intensive daily labour migration. The economic orientation of the municipalities in the region is diverse and shows a moderate concentration of activities in the service sector. These municipalities are characterized by areas of concentration, immigration and accelerated urbanization, as well as intensive daily migration directed mainly towards Ljubljana, the capital (MOP, 2019). Population density ranges between 1.065,4 inhabitants per km², in the most urbanised areas and 37,4 in the least urbanised areas (RRA LUR, 2022).

There are 6 administrative units (LAU 1) in the region (Domžale, Grosuplje, Kamnik, Ljubljana, Logatec and Vrhnika) (SURS, n.d.). While the average population in the 25 municipalities (LAU 2) of the region is about 22.200 inhabitants, this varies between about 3.000 (Horjul) and 293.000 (Ljubljana) (SURS, 2022).

Figure 1: Map of Osrednjeslovenska region with levels of settlements (MOP, 2019)

The region is characterized by a large proportion of preserved natural areas, especially in the hilly parts, and a large forest cover. Agricultural and forest areas cover most of the area (more than 50 %) and thus significantly determine the landscape image of the region. There are 67 ecologically important areas in the region, which are of great importance for the preservation of habitats and many plant and animal species. The Natura 2000 network covers 26,7 % of the region. (RRA LUR, 2022)

Figure 2: Municipalities in the Osrednjeslovenska region (RRA LUR, 2022)

Table 3 – Distribution of land use in the Pilot region (year 2022) (Source: Rural observatory)

	Pilot Region		Broader context (NUTS2 region)	
	hectares	%	hectares	%
Urban area	18.277	7,8%	37.007	4,7%
Industrial area	4.249	1,8%	6.501	0,8%
Forest area	144867	62,1%	544840	69,5%
Agricultural area	58873	25,2%	148107	18,9%

Infrastructure area	3830	1,6%	12195	1,6%
Natural area*	1600	0,7%	30740	3,9%
Abandoned area	186	0,1%	236	0,0%
Water bodies	620	0,3%	2011	0,3%
Urban green leisure	932	0,4%	2256	0,3%
Total area	233.434	100,0%	783.893	100,0%

*Natural area includes the following categories: shrubs; nature grassland, wetlands, other nature.

Table 4: breakdown of agricultural land uses in the PR

Crop type	ha	% of PR	% of agricultural área
Arable crops	27793	11,9%	47,21
Mixed crops livestock	399	0,2%	0,68
Livestock	30318	13,0%	51,50
Vineyard	155	0,1%	242,37
Fruit production	207	0,1%	0,06
Olive production	1	0,0%	0,26

1.2 Demographic change

Table 5 – Indicators of demographic change and comparison with regional level (SUR5)

Demographic indicators	Pilot Region			Broader region (NUTS2 – Zahodna Slovenija)		
	2000	2022	Annual change rate (%)	2000	2022	Annual change rate (%)
Total resident population (no. Inhabitants)	487.789	555.213	13,8	910.239	1.004.237	10,3
Total fertility rate (liveborn/1000 pop)	9,7	9,5 ^s		9,4	9,1 ^s	
Natural population change /1000 pop	1,5	0,1 ^s		0,9	-0,7 ^s	

Immigration rate /1000 pop	4,3	12,2 ^{\$}		3,8	12 ^{\$}	
Emigration rate /1000 pop	2,1	12,1 ^{\$}		2,1	11,1 ^{\$}	
Net migration rate /1000 pop	2,1	0,1 ^{\$}		1,8	0,9 ^{\$}	
Ageing index	85,1	122,7 ^{\$}		116,4*	132,95	
Old age dependency ratio	19,4	30,0		44*	56,6	

*2008 data; ^{\$}2021 data; migrations are shown for other countries

Figure 3: Classification of Slovenian municipalities in terms of rurality and population trends; Source: Nared et al., 2019.

The municipalities of the PR can generally be characterised as having positive population growth (Table 6), although there are still significant differences between them in terms of extent and the cause of this population change (Table 7); all municipalities are also characterised by aging of the population. Figure 3 shows the classification of Slovenian municipalities into categories in terms of their rurality and population increase/decrease; whether urban or rural, all municipalities in the pilot region show an increasing population trend.

The average age of residents in the PR is the lowest among Slovenian regions. According to data from 2019, the region is home to a high proportion (16.0%) of the population aged 0 to 14 and 18.4% of the population aged 65 or over, of which 5.2% are over 80, which is still below the Slovenian average (5.3% of the population). The old-age dependency ratio is also the lowest

among Slovenian regions. At the beginning of 2019, it was 52.3 (below the Slovenian average of 53.7). Since 2014, the old-age dependency ratio has increased by 5.4 in the region, and by 6.5 in Slovenia in the same period. This also increased the aging index, which stood at 115.1 in 2019, which is one of the lower aging indices in Slovenian regions (the Slovenian average in 2019 was 131.7) (RRA LUR, 2022).

Table 6: Demographic change per municipality (Source: SURS)

OBČINE	2008	2022	% change 2022/2008
Borovnica	3.921	4.629	18%
Brezovica	10.283	12.823	25%
Dobrepolje	3.705	3.871	4%
Dobrova - Polhov Gradec	7.120	7.844	10%
Dol pri Ljubljani	5.114	6.348	24%
Domžale	32.748	36.905	13%
Grosuplje	18.085	21.333	18%
Horjul	2.740	3.006	10%
Ig	6.098	7.695	26%
Ivančna Gorica	14.692	17.599	20%
Kamnik	28.266	29.793	5%
Komenda	4.849	6.482	34%
Ljubljana	267.760	293.218	10%
Log - Dragomer	3.484	3.681	6%
Logatec	12.410	14.699	18%
Lukovica	5.257	5.978	14%
Medvode	14.879	16.792	13%
Mengeš	6.969	8.487	22%
Moravče	4.807	5.522	15%
Škofljica	8.145	11.666	43%
Šmartno pri Litiji	5.278	5.700	8%
Trzin	3.664	3.900	6%
Velike Lašče	4.093	4.584	12%
Vodice	15.262	17.684	16%
Vrhnika	4.311	4.974	15%
Total	495.948	557.235	12%

Table 7: demographic indicators for PR municipalities

	2000						2021					
	Avg age	Ageing index	Old age dep	Fert rate /1000	Nat growth /1000	Total migration / 1000	Avg age	Ageing index	Old age dep	Fert rate /1000	Nat growth /1000	Total migration / 1000
Borovnica	37,9	77,4	19,0	9,8	1,1	5,6	41,2	96,6	28,2	8,8	0,6	-7,8
Brezovica	37,2	63,4	16,6	10,5	2,5	10,5	41,8	103,0	29,0	10,1	-1,4	2,6
Dobrepolje	38,5	84,9	24,9	12,7	0,0	3,4	43,3	126,4	30,2	9,5	-9,5	5,2
Dobrova - Polhov Gradec	37,2	71,2	19,8	11,0	3,9	11,3	41,4	101,4	28,4	10,6	3,3	-3,8
Dol pri Ljubljani	36,9	63,6	16,0	12,1	5,7	20,2	40,4	88,6	26,0	10,7	6,3	-9,9
Domžale	36,9	61,5	15,9	9,6	2,4	4,9	41,8	107,4	28,6	10,3	1,9	4,1
Grosuplje	36,4	60,0	16,3	12,2	4,9	11,2	40,9	94,8	26,0	10,0	0,4	-2,4
Horjul	35,7	56,7	16,9	16,4	11,8	2,3	43,2	123,6	37,2	11,3	-6,3	13,7
Ig	37,6	72,5	16,7	10,4	1,7	9,9	41,3	100,2	29,2	9,2	0,5	5,6
Ivančna Gorica	37,0	71,5	21,0	12,7	3,1	10,0	40,4	85,4	23,8	11,8	4,4	-0,1
Kamnik	37,5	73,1	18,2	11,4	2,6	5,3	42,4	115,1	29,8	9,8	0,6	-7,1
Komenda	36,1	57,6	14,7	11,5	5,0	3,7	38,9	73,0	23,0	9,3	2,8	4,9
Ljubljana	40,1	103,6	20,9	8,5	0,1	-4,1	42,7	139,0	30,1	9,0	-0,2	-4,9
Log - Dragomer	-	-	-	-	-	-	44,6	165,6	38,5	11,2	4,9	11,5
Logatec	35,7	55,5	17,1	12,1	4,5	6,3	40,6	89,0	26,2	10,3	-0,7	1,3
Lukovica	36,1	60,4	18,2	11,4	2,9	6,4	40,2	84,0	25,2	10,3	3,9	9,1
Medvode	38,1	78,9	18,0	10,0	3,3	11,2	43,1	124,6	32,9	9,3	-0,9	0,6
Mengeš	36,6	60,2	15,3	13,2	3,6	3,3	42,2	109,8	29,6	9,8	-4,8	11,0
Moravče	35,3	54,6	16,7	13,6	5,8	7,4	40,1	86,7	24,7	11,3	3,6	5,3
Škofljica	36,8	56,2	14,2	14,2	8,2	38,9	40,7	90,8	26,4	9,3	-1,7	0,6
Šmartno pri Litiji	-	-	-	-	-	-	42,7	119,2	32,5	11,3	-4,4	11,1
Trzin	37,3	58,4	11,1	11,4	5,2	43,1	43,7	140,3	38,7	9,0	-2,1	-6,2
Velike Lašče	39,9	109,3	27,5	9,6	0,5	8,0	42,7	118,6	32,1	11,3	1,3	12,8
Vodice	37,1	67,6	18,4	10,7	1,6	9,4	40,9	90,5	23,7	7,9	-0,2	0,6
Vrhnika	37,4	69,4	16,9	9,0	3,1	10,8	42,2	111,6	29,5	9,1	-0,8	3,5

1.3 The differentiated access to services within the Pilot Region and the differences with respect to the closest territories and in the regional/national economy.

Data on access to services in Slovenia are relatively poor and this information must in many cases be inferred from other sources and proxy indicators. For example, the lowest level of granularity for the information on number of hospital beds is the statistical region (582,84/100 000 people in the PR in 2021; NIJZ, 2023a). In 2021, there were 703 doctors in this region (NIJZ, 2023b). Similarly, the lowest level of granularity for social exclusion statistics is the statistical region.

Figure 4: Average access time (in minutes) from building locations to the nearest connection to the highway or expressway by RS municipalities in 2015. Source: Drobne, 2016

All parts of the PR can be considered reasonably well connected to highways and/or expressways (Figure 4), the time to reach an expressway or highway exceeds 30 minutes only in the municipalities Dobrepolje and Velike Lašče; a similar statement can be made of physical access to primary healthcare (Figure 5).

Public transport (bus and rail passenger transport) currently has the greatest potential for the development of sustainable mobility in the region. It is relatively well covered by public transport: 49% of residents live within 30 minutes of the city centre with all available public transport resources. Only 10% of the region's residents do not have access to public transport (a distance of 1,000 m along the footpath network). While the city public transportation system has seen an increase in the number of users between 2014 and 2017 by 1.5%, and an extension of the total length of lines by 2.6 km, the number of

users of the intercity public transportation system. A review of public transport timetables on intercity connections shows that public transport on these connections is still somewhat too slow, insufficiently frequent, unpredictable in time and price-competitive with personal motor transport. 8% of daily migrants regularly use public transport in the region. Estimates show that the maximum capacity of regional PPP vehicles (buses and trains together) during the morning rush hour (between 6 a.m. and 9 a.m.) is only about 18,000 seats, which is almost seven times less than the number of daily migrants to the region (RRA LUR, 2022). In October 2018, the Integrated Transport Strategy of the Ljubljana Urban Region (CPS LUR) was adopted with the aim of improving the long-term state of sustainable mobility and transport planning.

Figure 5: Location of healthcare facilities (at least at primary level) in Slovenia (Source: MZ, 2023)

Figure 6: Number of children per kindergarten in Slovenia. Source: SURS.

1.4 Structured forms of cooperation and partnerships (already in place).

The municipalities of the Ljubljana Urban Region (LUR, which unites the 25 municipalities of the PR) have decided to directly establish a regional council whose members are mayors of municipalities in the region. Professional, technical and administrative support for the operation of the LUR Council is provided by The Regional Development Agency of the Ljubljana Urban Region (RRA LUR), whose most important goals are 'coordinated economic development of the region, prudent use of natural resources, energy and space, sustainable mobility, utilization of creative potential and accessibility of user-friendly public services' (RRA LUR, 2023). RRA LUR is also responsible for the planning and preparation of the regional development programme, in which it defines the region's strategic orientations and development goals, as well as the instruments and resources for their realization. RRA LUR itself is a member of a number of national and transnational organisations, such as EURADA (European Association of Development Agencies) and Eurocities; it also cooperates in projects to increase the circularity and sustainability of its economy, such as the Interreg project ECOLE (ECO industrial park network for the Alpine Regions Leveraging smart and Circular Economy) and CER partnership.

At the national level, the largest body connecting municipalities is the Community of municipalities (Skupnost občin Slovenije), which unites over 180 of 212 Slovenian municipalities (though 5 of the PR municipalities are not in it, including Ljubljana). Its main function is to represent municipality interests with regard to the state administration (Skupnost občin, n.d.). In certain cases, it is authorised to represent Slovenian municipalities in international bodies, such as the Alps-Adriatic Alliance.

The municipalities in the region participate in a number of different Local Action groups (Lokalne akcijske skupine, LAS), listed in Table 8 and depicted in Figure 7. These organisations are coordinated and represented by the Slovenian Rural Development Network.

[Table 8: List of municipalities and LAGs in the programming period 2014-2020 \(Lokalne akcijske skupine v Sloveniji v programskem obdobju 2011-2020\) \(MKGP, 2018\)](#)

LAG	Municipalities
LAS Barje z zaledjem	Borovnica, Brezovica, Dobrova - Polhov Gradec, Horjul, Log – Dragomer, Vrhnika
LAS Po poteh dediščine od Turjaka do Kolpe	Dobrepolje, Velike Lašče
LAS s CILjem	Logatec
LAS Sožitje	Grosuplje, Ig, Ljubljana, Škofljica
LAS Srce Slovenije	Dol pri Ljubljani, Kamnik, Lukovica, Moravče, Šmartno pri Litiji
LAS Suhe krajine, Temenice in Krke	Ivančna Gorica
LAS za mesto in vas	Domžale, Komenda, Medvode, Mengeš, Trzin, Vodice

Figure 7: Local action groups in Slovenia in the period 2014-2020 (MKGP, 2018)

2. The emerging functions of the Pilot Region

NATIONAL GUIDELINES

According to the **Guidelines for the development of the Osrednjeslovenska region, published by the Ministry of environment and spatial planning (2019)**, the main development potentials for the region are in services, research and creative activities and tourism. On the other hand, compared to the rest of Slovenia, the region is characterized by the smallest area of utilised agricultural area, which at the same time represents land important for the supply of urban settlements in region with food.

Priority areas intended for the concentration of economic activities meet the needs of several local communities (municipalities) at the same time and thereby concentrate the development potential of the region. In urban settlements that perform the function of centres of I. and II., and exceptionally III. level, in accordance with the provision of optimal and rational accessibility, the conditions for the development of larger production plants and highly developed service activities are to be ensured. In Ljubljana, as a centre of international importance, the vision described in the guidelines is to develop nationally

important technological and industrial parks and promote the concentration of economic activities. Preference is given to the renovation and reactivation of degraded areas with before encroachment on new surfaces. Housing supply is to be preferentially directed to urban settlements identified as the most suitable: Ljubljana, Domžale, Kamnik, Grosuplje, Logatec, Škofljica, Lavrica, Trzin, and Borovnica.

In priority areas dedicated to tourism, further development will focus on the unburdening, renovation and reuse of existing tourist capacities in terms of increasing the quality of accommodation, services and programmes, reducing water and waste use, and improving the infrastructure for sustainable mobility and accessibility by means of public transport even for the last kilometre. Instead of opening new areas, the focus should be on areas where key tourist infrastructure is already provided in the region based on the definition of tourist destinations in the Tourism Strategy. A distinct spatial potential for the development of cultural and congress tourism is seen as present in Ljubljana, which is at the same time the starting point for the tourist region and recreationally interesting areas in the nearby less urbanised areas (e.g. the Savinjske Alps, the Polhograjski Dolomites, Ljubljana Marshes, Šmarna Gora, Rašica). The spatial potential for the development of tourism is also preserved and strengthened in the old town centres present in the region (Kamnik, Vrhnika). The settlements of Rakitna and Polhov Gradec are also seen as having spatial potential as secondary tourist settlements and should be developed for the needs of the region's mountain sports and recreation centres (Krvavec, Velika planina), while areas along the rivers Sava and Ljubljanica are appropriate to be developed for water sports.

Agricultural land with the greatest production potential in the wider urban area of Ljubljana and in the vicinity of urban settlements should preferentially be used for agriculture, especially for the production of food for the supply of cities and for the creation of short local supply chains, reduction of transport costs and burden on the environment, with the support of the green public procurement system. The economic and social role of agriculture in ensuring the vitality and population of the region's rural areas is to be promoted.

The framework of the green system in the region is formed by a connected system of over 50 Natura 2000 sites. Among the larger ones are the Krimsko hribovje, Trnovski gozd, part of the Kamniško Savinjske Alps and Rašica. In Natura 2000 areas, the conditions for maintaining a favourable state of habitats should be ensured. Landscape areas with recognizable characteristics, important at the national level, located in the area of the Central Slovenian region are: the areas of Ljubljana marshes, Planinsko polje, Polhov Gradec - Črni Vrh, Radensko polje, Smlednik, Šmarna gora, Velika planina, Volčji potok and Dolsko - Krumperk. These landscape areas represent the potential for tourist or leisure activities, where it is possible to create high-quality and diverse and regionally recognizable tourist products, therefore the strategy for the development of the region also takes into account the guidelines for priority areas for the development of individual activities, which are important for the development of the region. In the hinterland of

Ljubljana and other urban settlements, the possibility of mixed use of agricultural and forest areas for recreational purposes should be exploited.

It is also considered that the region should cooperate and connect with the Gorenjska Development Region in the formation of a wider Central Slovenian urban area and functional integration in this area. It should also cooperate and connect with neighboring areas or development regions within the framework of the green infrastructure system at the regional level and in developing social infrastructure and public infrastructure in the field of environment and transport.

RRA LUR DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

The region's own **development strategy, published by the RRA LUR development agency (2022)**, echoes these guidelines to a great degree. It is seen necessary to ensure favourable infrastructural and socio-economic conditions for the development of the economy and the promotion of entrepreneurship in the future, with an emphasis on attracting highly qualified labour and capital. This is to be achieved through international integration and strengthening of innovation in the region, as well as increasing competitiveness and recognition in the international environment.

In addition to the economic and technological development potential residing in quickly growing firms, its central role as a research hub and creativity, the strategy emphasises the great potential of the region manifested in a holistic consideration of the opportunities offered by the **transition from a linear to a circular economy** and the development of appropriate economic models, with an emphasis on the efficient use of resources, the selection of materials, reuse and smart consumption of all generations and social groups. An example given is wood, as the region is relatively forested: over half of the area is agricultural and forested. Relatedly, and with the aim of fostering sustainable development, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and building a circular economy, it is seen as expedient to focus on the renewed or faster development of the wood processing industry and greater use of wood in the construction of buildings while using the residues from use and processing for energy purposes.

In the view of the Strategy's authors, the circular economy opens up new business opportunities for companies through the transformation of business models. The potential of the region is thus seen as manifested in the implementation of projects that will enable companies to transform their business models to create circular solutions and exchange resources (in industrial symbiosis). In this vision, the region will turn the challenge of promoting sustainable growth into an opportunity and focus efforts on increasing the social responsibility of producers and consumers.

In 2018, the Ljubljana Urban Region was recognized by the European Commission as one of the six European regions that have the potential to encourage SMEs in the transition

to a circular economy. At the same time, Ljubljana, as an important regional centre, is placed on the European map of sustainable cities (Green European Capital 2016, inclusion in the "Circular Cities" network, the first European "No Waste" capital), which with its activities significantly contributes to the transition to a circular economy.

Creative industries (occupations) represent the largest occupational group of the working population in the region, followed by service, manufacturing and agricultural occupations. One of the main potentials of LUR is thus the possibility of (even) more active integration of creative occupations with other industrial sectors and numerous educational and research institutions in the region. As the capital, Ljubljana is the creative centre of Slovenia and the region, which is changing from a centre of cultural consumption to a centre of cultural production. However, the such occupations, dominated by the self-employed and SMEs, represents an obstacle to establishment on international markets, as evidenced by the sector's low export orientation.

The strategic development of **tourism** has 3 main priorities: increasing competitiveness through improving the quality of infrastructure and tourist offer; environmental conservation and sustainable resource use; and sustainable mobility. Linking with the Gorenjska region to form a macro-destination is also foreseen.

The strategy sees rural development as inextricably interlinked with the development of **agriculture and forestry**. In addition to the economic importance of agriculture and food production, its other functions are also highlighted, as it is seen as maintaining rural settlements and contributing to the development of other rural activities, such as tourism, crafts and the preservation of cultural heritage and landscapes. Agriculture also performs an important function in the environmental field and from a territorial point of view.

From an economic point of view, there great potential is seen in sustainable food production, food security, the expansion and integration of production for the market, and the organization of food value chains - including the processing and marketing of agricultural and traditional products both locally and regionally. The market niche is primarily organically produced food, as the demand for it from Slovenian consumers is constantly growing, and the offer from domestic production cannot meet demand. Important segments are the promotion of the transfer of knowledge and innovations in agriculture, forestry and the wood processing industry, the preservation of the cultural heritage of the countryside and the transfer and revival of traditional and specific knowledge and skills, as well as the presentation of these professions as attractive and entrepreneurially oriented. The implementation of innovative technologies in agriculture and wood production is also a potential and a challenge. At the same time, we must wood is highlighted as a natural material for the construction of buildings and a renewable source of energy.

From an environmental point of view, the potential of agriculture and forestry lies in the sustainable management of natural resources and raw materials. Furthermore, the significant contribution of the agricultural sector to climate change, which is increasingly changing the conditions for food production and animal husbandry, is mentioned, as well

as the (limited) ability of the agricultural sector to mitigate climate change should in relation to maintaining or increasing the scale of food production.

From a spatial point of view, the potential of agriculture is seen as lying in balanced spatial development and the parallel preservation of high-quality agricultural areas of great ecological importance. The cultural (agricultural) landscape as a public good has an important place in the future development of agriculture. In areas that are more difficult to access, where highly competitive production is not expected, the potential lies in the combination of income sources and the development of niche products with high value-added.

Solar energy and hydropower, as well as wood biomass and geothermal energy for heat production, represent the greatest potential for **electricity production**. In terms of hydropower, the planned chain of hydroelectric power plants on the upper/middle Sava (HE Jevnica) is important for the region. The share of wood biomass utilization at the regional level is much lower than the share at the national level. Abiding by the principles of sustainable forest management and through restarting the wood industry, it represents a great potential. Rural municipalities such as Borovnica, Dobropolje, Ig, Ivančna Gorica, Logatec, Lukovica, Šmartno pri Litiji and Velike Lašče have the best opportunities for using wood biomass.

3. Main differences between rural areas within the Pilot Region

Based on the information listed so far, the municipalities in the region could be roughly divided into the central urban area, intermediate (peri-urban) areas with a lower population density and strong presence of agriculture and forestry, and relatively remote and agricultural rural areas with somewhat lower incomes. However, even this classification seems a little forced, as there is a strong presence of agriculture even in the more urbanised municipalities with higher incomes per capita.

Table 9: characteristics of farming and gross income per inhabitant in the region's municipalities, 2020 (Source: SURS)

	Number of agricultural holdings	Utilised agricultural area (ha)	Livestock units (LU)	LU/ha	Gross income (EUR / inhabitant)		
					uaa/ah	lu/ah	
Borovnica	98	872	606	0,70	8,90	6,183673	13328,91
Brezovica	251	2863	2105	0,74	11,41	8,386454	14652,37
Dobropolje	288	1550	933	0,60	5,38	3,239583	13397,50

Dobrova - Polhov Gradec	350	2.921	2.992	1,02	8,35	8,548571	13898,32
Dol pri Ljubljani	138	942	914	0,97	6,83	6,623188	14940,92
Domžale	276	3270	4106	1,26	11,85	14,87681	14949,23
Grosuplje	497	3890	3459	0,89	7,83	6,959759	14695,83
Horjul	144	976	909	0,93	6,78	6,3125	13597,97
Ig	315	2962	1804	0,61	9,40	5,726984	13888,30
Ivančna Gorica	954	5995	5351	0,89	6,28	5,609015	14361,06
Kamnik	720	4507	6465	1,43	6,26	8,979167	13898,54
Komenda	83	1072	1252	1,17	12,92	15,08434	14843,76
Ljubljana	791	5379	6070	1,13	6,80	7,673831	15391,98
Log - Dragomer	39	430	399	0,93	11,03	10,23077	18939,66
Logatec	421	3241	2890	0,89	7,70	6,864608	13934,56
Lukovica	347	2421	2931	1,21	6,98	8,446686	13548,64
Medvode	215	1649	2007	1,22	7,67	9,334884	15085,39
Mengeš	33	166	111	0,67	5,03	3,363636	14959,42
Moravče	354	2173	2298	1,06	6,14	6,491525	13228,83
Škofljica	163	1284	894	0,70	7,88	5,484663	15972,58
Šmartno pri Litiji	336	2264	2540	1,12	6,74	7,559524	12691,66
Trzin	17	111	141	1,27	6,53	8,294118	17062,46
Velike Lašče	316	1984	1308	0,66	6,28	4,139241	13954,95
Vodice	122	1051	1591	1,51	8,61	13,04098	16544,22
Vrhnika	272	3426	2736	0,80	12,60	10,05882	14522,11

According to the RRA LUR strategy (2022), the PR has a polycentric system of settlement with a high concentration and development of central and service activities. Geomorphological characteristics and traffic corridors have the greatest influence on the settlement of LUR. From the dense urban core within the motorway ring of Ljubljana, the settlement spreads in a star pattern in 5 development directions, namely towards the NW (Medvode–Škofja Loka–Kranj), towards the N (Trzin–Domžale–Kamnik), towards the E (Dol-Litija), towards the SE (Škofljica–Šmarje-Sap–Grosuplje), and towards SW (Brezovica–Borovnica–Vrhnika). These are the areas of employment centres and their hinterlands, which stretch especially along the highway system, and the areas between them are dominated by scattered construction. The spatially and environmentally negative trend of intensive construction continues in these areas of scattered construction outside the public passenger transport corridors.

There are nine urban settlements with city status in the region. The regional centre of Ljubljana is also a national centre of international importance. As a major research, education and employment centre, it is the destination of a large number of daily migrations within the region as well as from other regions. Ljubljana is the centre of the first level, where administrative functions of the highest level are maintained and developed. Domžale and Kamnik are centres of the third level with service, maintenance

and other activities that are necessary to supply the urban core and its gravitational hinterland of predominantly rural character. Logatec, Vrhnika and Grosuplje are centres of the fourth level, in which care at the primary level and the territorial organization of the state administration are being developed.

Other settlements in the region are insufficiently equipped with central functions. The situation is further worsened by the negative trend of centralization of local care functions (medical centres, post offices, banks, etc.), which lowers the quality of living and generates an additional traffic burden in larger urban centres. Settlements are also inadequately prepared for the aging of the population, which will become a significant problem in the near future.

In the entire region, but especially in Ljubljana and its surroundings, the housing problem is very pronounced, as there is a lack of affordable housing, which is a consequence of the centralization of the state and alternative forms of rental for tourist purposes. Furthermore, reducing daily migration remains the biggest challenge, while the tool for achieving it remains polycentric development of the region, which will be used to reduce the need for migration and promote sustainable mobility by modernizing railway transport and PPP. (RRA LUR, 2022)

4. The main transition challenges

According to the development strategy of RRA LUR (2022), the key challenges faced by the LUR are: daily migration, which is a result of the marked centralization of services in its centre, the negative consequences of traffic (e.g. pollutant emissions, noise, accidents, traffic jams), a large proportion of young job seekers and the departure of the educated workforce from regions. Likewise, in the LUR, which consists of 25 municipalities, in almost half of the municipalities, the need to invest in the construction of drinking water supply infrastructure has been assessed, and large needs for investments in waste water drainage and treatment in agglomerations under 2,000 PE have also been recorded. The region is characterized by a large number of areas at risk of flooding, which partially limit the development of the region. In Slovenia, Ljubljana is one of the potentially most flood-prone areas, and 15 of the 25 municipalities in the LUR are among the municipalities with a high degree of risk due to floods.

That said, it should be highlighted that since the beginning of the activities of the Slovenian Living lab, partners have agreed to focus on the issue of food waste and its relation to aspects of social inclusion and social entrepreneurship. The actors gathered under the Living lab have agreed that this offers a fruitful avenue of action in the region, while also addressing significant data gaps that are known to exist in this particular field from past and ongoing research projects, as well as activities of the agricultural and

environmental ministry. The focus group and meetings that have been conducted by the drafting of this report have centred around forming an appropriate group of actors to participate in the tackling of this particular challenge and agreeing to pool knowledge and existing resource to reduce this data gap. Tackling the issue of food waste is seen by the LL's actors as central to a circular economy with linked agricultural value chains and a significantly decreased climate and environmental footprint, as well as an inclusive society; acquiring and collating the relevant information with regard to this is seen as being among the central tasks of the Living lab. Furthermore, there has been agreement that, in this region, the relation between rural and urban areas is tightly knit and should therefore be considered in the project's work.

5. The state of knowledge and information needs

The main issue with analysing the relevant economic, social and environmental processes occurring in the Pilot Region is most probably the lack of data for all the relevant indicators at a sufficient level of granularity.

With regard to the specific issue tackled by the Living lab, there is a big data gap in the quantification and characterisation of different food loss and waste streams per segment of food value chain and at the appropriate level of granularity. A recent analysis at the level of national data estimated that the Slovenian methodology for estimating the amount of food waste is adequate and is also being developed accordingly. On the other hand, in Slovenia we do not have data or estimates on food losses that occur in production up to and including offering for sale, on the amount of food surpluses that occur at all stages of the food supply chain, on the amount and types of use of side streams of food production and on the method and amount of redistribution of surplus food by donating food to help people in need. These flows are partially and in varying detail recorded in various individual state and private records, which can be the starting point for establishing a monitoring system at the state level (Osojnik Črnivec et al., 2021).

6. Conclusions

The Pilot region represents an interesting conglomerate of urban and rural municipalities, with most of the municipalities generally characterised by population growth. In many of the municipalities, farming is still among the main forms of land use. There are notable income disparities within the region and differences between areas of concentrating population and more marginal areas.

In the field of food loss and waste, PR actors have highlighted the need for better data collected at a central level and with a sufficient level of quality to justify practical and policy action. As

indicated, these data are only under development at the national level. This has also been identified as one of the foremost needs of the Living lab, which requires close cooperation between LL actors in order to first pinpoint leverage points for action and then stimulate cooperation between value chain, non-profit and policy actors. In addition, the Living lab intends to assess the social impact of addressing the issue in an inclusive manner, which is characterised by a lack of standardised methodologies and data sources.

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